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Supplement A

Take thread tile size 6×4 , workgroup size 16×16 as an example:
The horizontal axis is the number of workgroups, which correspond to the size $m \times n$ of matrix C.
For example, 60 workgroups correspond to $m \times n = 3,686,490$ and 900 workgroups correspond to $m \times n = 5,529,600$. The performance of rocBLAS with default configuration is lower.

Fig A.1

According to the test results in [1], the performance of hipBLAS and MAGMA's DGEMM is lower than Tensile tuned rocBLAS. We can add the comparison if necessary.

Fig. 2. Performance of the GEMM operation in double precision on the Mi50 GPU. Results are shown for square sizes using ROCm 3.5.

Reference

[1] [Brown C, Abdelfattah A, Tomov S, et al. Design, optimization, and benchmarking of dense linear algebra algorithms on AMD GPUs\[C\]//2020 IEEE High Performance Extreme Computing Conference \(HPEC\). IEEE, 2020: 1-7.](#)

Supplement B

Experiments on MI50.

For threadtile 6*4, workgroup size 16*16:

The horizontal axis is the number of workgroups, which correspond to the size $m * n$ of matrix C. For example, 60 workgroups correspond to $m * n = 3,686,490$, 1500 workgroups correspond to $m * n = 9,216,000$.

Fig B.1

Supplement C

(1)(2)(3)(4) for threadtile 4*4, (5)(6)(7)(8) for threadtile 6*4.

There are four situations, for easy discussion:

DB: using Double Buffer

NP: without prefetching

FGPS: using FGPS

FGNP: using FG without prefetching

It is easy to see that NP and FGPS use the same number of registers for 4*4 thread tile size. For 4*6 and 6*4 thread tile sizes, FGPS use 4 less registers than NP.

FGNP uses 8 less registers than FGPS, but need more LDS read instructions and the pipeline can not cover the latency entirely even if the FGNP can enable one more workgroup to be scheduled on one SIMD engine.

Supplement D

Actual performance numbers on MI50

TABLE D.1 Performance(Tflop/s) of double buffer and FGPS with threadtile 6*4

M=N=K(*768)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
DB_6x4	4.18	5.56	5.66	5.85	5.88	5.95	5.91	5.97	6.00	5.97	5.99	6.04	6.02	6.04	6.02	6.01	6.04	6.03	6.03	6.02
FGPS_6x4	3.81	5.44	5.70	5.84	6.00	6.07	6.07	6.13	6.12	6.16	6.14	6.17	6.17	6.17	6.19	6.19	6.18	6.19	6.18	6.18
improvement(%)	-8.9	-2.1	0.7	-0.3	2.1	2.0	2.7	2.6	1.9	3.1	2.7	2.2	2.6	2.1	2.8	2.9	2.2	2.7	2.6	2.8

TABLE D.2 Performance(Tflop/s) of double buffer and FGPS with threadtile 4x4

M=N=K(*512)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
DB_4x4	2.51	5.07	4.92	5.36	5.21	5.42	5.35	5.48	5.43	5.42	5.47	5.52	5.49	5.50	5.49	5.50	5.51	5.54	5.52	5.53
FGPS_4x4	2.42	5.47	5.30	5.82	5.69	5.92	5.83	5.98	5.91	6.00	5.96	5.99	6.00	6.03	6.01	6.04	6.01	6.05	6.02	6.05
improvement(%)	-3.5	8.0	7.7	8.6	9.3	9.2	9.0	9.0	8.8	10.7	9.0	8.6	9.2	9.5	9.6	9.7	9.1	9.2	9.1	9.4

Supplement E

For threadtile 6*4, workgroup size 16*16:

The heatmap of *A* transposition and *B* transposition correspond to in Fig. 9.

Fig E.1

Supplement F

For threadtile 4*4, workgroup size 32*16, the test results using AMD ROCm Profiler are listed below:

M*N	VALUBusy		MemUnitBusy		LDSBankConflict		MemUnitStalled		ALUStalledByLDS		VALUInsts	
	DB	FGPS	DB	FGPS	DB	FGPS	DB	FGPS	DB	FGPS	DB	FGPS
368,640	72	70	18	15	0	0	1	1	16	1	12375	12375
737,280	77	83	19	17	0	0	1	1	8	6	12375	12375
1,105,920	79	85	19	18	0	0	1	1	6	3	12375	12375
1,474,560	80	87	20	19	0	0	0	1	4	3	12375	12375
1,843,200	80	88	19	19	0	0	1	1	3	2	12375	12375
2,211,840	81	89	18	20	0	0	1	0	3	2	12375	12375
2,580,480	82	89	18	18	0	0	1	0	2	1	12375	12375
2,949,120	82	90	18	19	0	0	1	1	2	1	12375	12375
3,317,760	82	90	18	19	0	0	1	0	2	1	12375	12375
3,686,400	82	90	18	19	0	0	1	1	1	1	12375	12375
4,055,040	82	90	18	19	0	0	1	0	1	1	12375	12375
4,423,680	83	91	18	19	0	0	0	0	1	1	12375	12375
4,792,320	83	91	18	19	0	0	0	0	1	1	12375	12375
5,160,960	83	91	18	20	0	0	0	0	1	1	12375	12375
5,529,600	83	91	18	20	0	0	0	0	1	0	12375	12375

VALUBusy : The percentage of GPUtime vector ALU instructions are processed. Value range: 0% (bad) to 100% (optimal).

MemUnitBusy : The percentage of GPUtime the memory unit is active. The result includes the stall time (MemUnitStalled). This is measured with all extra fetches and writes and any cache or memory effects taken into account. Value range: 0% to 100% (fetch-bound).

MemUnitStalled : The percentage of GPUtime the memory unit is stalled. Try reducing the number or size of fetches and writes if possible. Value range: 0% (optimal) to 100% (bad).

ALUStalledByLDS : The percentage of GPUtime ALU units are stalled by the LDS input queue being full or the output queue being not ready. If there are LDS bank conflicts, reduce them. Otherwise, try reducing the number of LDS accesses if possible. Value range: 0% (optimal) to 100% (bad).

The VALUBusy is the main factor that affect the performance.

Prediction depicts the percentage improvements predicted by formula (1)&(2).
 VALUBusy depicts the percentage differences in VALUBusy measured by profiler.
 Flops depicts the percentage improvements of measured performances.